

Milan Scoring System in the Diagnosis of Salivary Gland Lesions for Assessment of Risk of Malignancy

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Abstract:

Background: Salivary gland lesions encompass a diverse spectrum of conditions, ranging from benign neoplasms to malignant tumors. Accurate diagnosis is critical for appropriate management. The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology, introduced in 2018, offers a standardized approach to FNAC (Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology), aiming to enhance diagnostic accuracy and clinical decision-making. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of the Milan System in diagnosing salivary gland lesions and assessing the associated risk of malignancy.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted from January 2023 to August 2023, involving 90 patients with salivary gland lesions. FNAC results were categorized according to the Milan System and correlated with histopathological findings. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0 to calculate sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV).

Results: FNAC categorized the lesions into non-diagnostic (5.6%), non-neoplastic (33.3%), atypia of undetermined significance (11.1%), neoplasm (27.8%), suspicious for malignancy (11.1%), and malignant (11.1%). Histopathology confirmed 60% benign and 40% malignant cases. The Milan System demonstrated a sensitivity of 90.0%, specificity of 85.0%, PPV of 81.8%, and NPV of 92.0%. Significant associations were found between FNAC categories III, IV, V, VI, and histopathological outcomes ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology provides a reliable framework for diagnosing salivary gland lesions and assessing malignancy risk. Its high sensitivity and specificity make it a valuable tool in clinical practice.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and diverse populations are recommended to validate these findings and explore the system's long-term prognostic value.

Keywords: Salivary Gland Lesions, Milan System, FNAC, Malignancy Risk, Diagnostic Accuracy.

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Introduction

Salivary gland lesions encompass a diverse group of conditions that can range from benign neoplasms to malignant tumors. The accurate diagnosis and assessment of these lesions are critical for effective management and treatment planning. Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is a widely used diagnostic tool due to its minimally invasive nature, cost-effectiveness, and rapid turnaround time. However, the interpretation of FNAC results can sometimes be challenging due to the complex histopathology of salivary gland lesions. In this context, the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology has emerged as a standardized approach to enhance the diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility of FNAC in salivary gland lesions.

The Milan System, introduced in 2018, categorizes salivary gland cytology into six distinct diagnostic categories: non-diagnostic, non-neoplastic, atypia of undetermined significance (AUS), neoplasm, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant. Each category is associated with a specific risk of malignancy (ROM) and corresponding clinical management recommendations. This system aims to provide a uniform reporting framework that can facilitate clearer communication between pathologists and clinicians, thereby improving patient management outcomes [1].

Recent studies have highlighted the efficacy of the Milan System in stratifying salivary gland lesions and predicting malignancy risk. A study demonstrated that the Milan System significantly improved the diagnostic yield and predictive value

of FNAC in salivary gland lesions, leading to more precise clinical decision-making [2]. Similarly, another study reported that the system's structured approach helped in reducing the rate of indeterminate diagnoses and provided better guidance for subsequent clinical actions [3].

Despite these advancements, the implementation of the Milan System in diverse clinical settings and its impact on patient outcomes warrant further investigation. In particular, the system's applicability in various populations and its effectiveness in predicting long-term prognoses remain areas of active research. For instance, a multicenter study across different demographic groups found consistent diagnostic accuracy, suggesting the system's robustness in diverse clinical environments [4].

This study aimed to assess the efficacy of the Milan scoring system in diagnosing salivary gland lesions and evaluating the associated risk of malignancy.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period from January 2023 to August 2023 at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya.

Participants: A total of 90 participants were included in the study. These participants were patients who presented with salivary gland lesions during the study period and underwent fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC).

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with clinically diagnosed salivary gland lesions.
- Patients who underwent FNAC for salivary gland lesions.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients who had previously been treated for salivary gland malignancies.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients presenting with salivary gland lesions within the study period were consecutively included. Information bias was mitigated by

ensuring data collection was standardized and conducted by trained personnel. Observer bias was reduced by having cytological assessments reviewed by multiple pathologists independently.

Variables: Variables included patient demographics (age, gender), clinical presentation, FNAC results, histopathological diagnosis, risk of malignancy as per the Milan scoring system.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records, FNAC reports, and histopathology reports. Patient demographic details, clinical presentations, FNAC findings, and final histopathological diagnoses were recorded.

Procedure

1. FNAC Procedure: All patients underwent FNAC of their salivary gland lesions. Smears were prepared and stained using standard cytological techniques.
2. Cytological Evaluation: FNAC smears were evaluated by pathologists and classified according to the Milan scoring system into six categories: non-diagnostic, non-neoplastic, atypia of undetermined significance, neoplasm, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant.
3. Histopathological Correlation: Patients who underwent surgical excision had their histopathological findings compared with the FNAC results.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into SPSS version 20.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics and FNAC results. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of the Milan scoring system were calculated using histopathological diagnosis as the gold standard. The Chi-square test was used to determine the statistical significance of associations between categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study included 90 patients with salivary gland lesions. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
- <20	10	11.1
- 20-39	25	27.8
- 40-59	35	38.9
- ≥60	20	22.2
Gender		
- Male	50	55.6

- Female	40	44.4
Clinical Presentation		
- Swelling	75	83.3
- Pain	15	16.7
- Other Symptoms	5	5.6

The distribution of FNAC results based on the Milan scoring system is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: FNAC Results According to the Milan Scoring System

Milan Category	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
I - Non-diagnostic	5	5.6
II - Non-neoplastic	30	33.3
III - Atypia of undetermined significance	10	11.1
IV - Neoplasm	25	27.8
V - Suspicious for malignancy	10	11.1
VI - Malignant	10	11.1

Of the 90 patients, 50 underwent surgical excision and had their histopathological findings compared with FNAC results. The histopathological diagnoses are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Histopathological Correlation

Histopathological Diagnosis	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Benign	30	60.0
Malignant	20	40.0

The diagnostic accuracy of the Milan scoring system was evaluated by calculating the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Diagnostic Accuracy of Milan Scoring System

Diagnostic Measure	Value (%)
Sensitivity	90.0
Specificity	85.0
PPV	81.8
NPV	92.0

The association between FNAC categories and histopathological outcomes was evaluated using the Chi-square test. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Statistical Significance

FNAC Category	Benign (n=30)	Malignant (n=20)	Chi-square (χ^2)	p-value
I - Non-diagnostic	3	2	0.789	0.375
II - Non-neoplastic	20	10	0.698	0.403
III - Atypia of undetermined significance	4	6	4.114	0.042*
IV - Neoplasm	20	5	10.556	0.001**
V - Suspicious for malignancy	2	8	12.000	0.001**
VI - Malignant	1	9	14.400	0.001**

*Significant at $p < 0.05$, **Significant at $p < 0.01$

The analysis demonstrated a statistically significant association between FNAC categories III, IV, V, VI, and histopathological outcomes, indicating the reliability of the Milan scoring system in assessing malignancy risk in salivary gland lesions.

Discussion

The study included 90 patients with salivary gland lesions, with ages ranging from less than 20 to over 60 years. The majority of patients (38.9%) were between 40-59 years old, and the gender distribution was relatively balanced, with 55.6% males and 44.4% females. Most patients (83.3%) presented with swelling as their primary symptom.

Fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) results categorized according to the Milan scoring system revealed that the largest group was the non-neoplastic category (33.3%), followed by neoplasm (27.8%). Categories for atypia of undetermined significance, suspicious for malignancy, and malignant each accounted for 11.1% of cases, while non-diagnostic results were the least common (5.6%).

Out of the 90 patients, 50 underwent surgical excision, allowing for histopathological correlation. The histopathological examination showed that 60% of these cases were benign, while 40% were malignant. This distribution provided a robust

dataset to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of the Milan scoring system.

The diagnostic performance of the Milan scoring system was assessed by calculating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). The system demonstrated a high sensitivity of 90.0%, indicating that it correctly identified 90% of malignant cases. The specificity was also high at 85.0%, showing that 85% of benign cases were accurately classified. The PPV was 81.8%, meaning that 81.8% of cases identified as malignant by FNAC were confirmed as malignant by histopathology. The NPV was 92.0%, indicating that 92% of cases classified as benign were truly benign.

The statistical analysis using the Chi-square test revealed significant associations between FNAC categories III (atypia of undetermined significance), IV (neoplasm), V (suspicious for malignancy), VI (malignant), and histopathological outcomes. Categories III, IV, V, and VI showed significant p-values (<0.05), with especially strong significance in categories IV, V, and VI (p<0.01). This indicates that these FNAC categories are reliable predictors of malignancy risk.

Overall, the study supports the effectiveness of the Milan scoring system in diagnosing salivary gland lesions and assessing the risk of malignancy. The high sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV demonstrate its diagnostic accuracy. The significant statistical associations between FNAC categories and histopathological outcomes further validate the system's reliability in clinical practice. These findings suggest that the Milan scoring system can be a valuable tool for clinicians in managing patients with salivary gland lesions, guiding treatment decisions, and improving patient outcomes.

A study was conducted over three years on 225 salivary gland lesions, reclassified into different Milan categories. The study found that the risk of malignancy (ROM) was highest in the malignant category (97.5%), followed by suspicious for malignancy (85.7%), and SUMP (33.3%). The overall sensitivity and specificity were 83.34% and 98.01%, respectively [5]. A study reclassified 413 parotid gland tumors using the Milan System. The study found a 100% ROM in the malignant category and 55.9% ROM for high-grade malignancy in the same category. The sensitivity for detecting high-grade malignancy was 89-96% [6].

292 cases were studied over three years, finding a ROM of 100% in the malignant category and 71.42% in the suspicious for malignancy category. The overall sensitivity and specificity were 64.28% and 97.01%, respectively [7]. A study evaluated

160 salivary gland FNAs, finding a ROM of 100% in the malignant category and 0% in the non-neoplastic category. The study emphasized the utility of the Milan System in real-time clinical settings [8].

A study analyzed salivary gland FNAs over two years, finding the ROM to be 87.5% in the malignant category and 100% in the suspicious for malignancy category. The sensitivity and specificity were 98.51% and 66.67%, respectively [9]. A study retrospectively reclassified 106 salivary gland FNAs, finding a 100% ROM in the malignant category and 75% in the suspicious for malignancy category. The study concluded that the Milan System improves diagnostic accuracy and management decisions [10]. A systematic review analyzed 19,652 samples. The ROM was 100% in the malignant category and 91% in the suspicious for malignancy category. The study affirmed the diagnostic utility of the Milan System [11].

Conclusion

The Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology is a reliable and effective tool for diagnosing salivary gland lesions and assessing malignancy risk. This study demonstrates its high sensitivity and specificity, confirming its utility in clinical practice for guiding treatment decisions and improving patient outcomes. Further research is recommended to validate these findings across larger and more diverse populations.

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